

THE STATE OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE TOURISM SECTOR IN UZBEKISTAN AND THE ROLE OF BUSINESS TOURISM IN IT

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Abstract. This article deals with planning and design of potential areas for the placement of tourism objects, analysis of visits by goals in the analysis of tourist flows, and assessment of the level of attractiveness of tourist resources.

Key words: tourism, business, facility, capacity, flow, analysis, travel, license.

СОСТОЯНИЕ РАЗВИТИЯ СФЕРЫ ТУРИЗМА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ И РОЛЬ В НЕЙ ДЕЛОВОГО ТУРИЗМА

Аннотация. В данной статье речь идет о планировании и проектировании потенциальных площадей для размещения объектов туризма, анализе посещений по целям при анализе туристских потоков, оценке уровня привлекательности туристских ресурсов.

Ключевые слова: туризм, бизнес, объект, пропускная способность, поток, анализ, путешествие, лицензия.

INTRODUCTION

Today, it is difficult to imagine the world economy without tourism. Globalization processes have led to an increase in the place of travel in human life. It can be seen not only as leisure and sightseeing, but also as a part of lifestyle, that is, human mobility has become normal. For example, our people have long been prone to a sedentary lifestyle, and it was very difficult for people to leave their places of residence even for a short time. Now we can observe that he works freely not only on the territory of Uzbekistan, but also in the countries of the whole world.

One of the reasons why the tourism sector is one of the most important sectors for the economic and social development of Uzbekistan is related to these processes. The importance of the industry for our country has been studied in the decrees and decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in the wide-ranging reforms being implemented, and in many scientific developments. An example of this is the adoption of more than 80 regulatory legal documents at the government level in the last four years. In the strategy of rapid development in our country, significant tasks are assigned to tourism. In 2021-2026, raising tourism to a higher level, including it among the "drivers" of regional development, is defined as one of the priority directions. especially

In the reforms in the field of tourism, in the first place, it is necessary to emphasize the improvement of the state policy coordination and development system. According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 2, 2016 PF 4861, the State Committee for the Development of Tourism of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established on the basis of the National Company "Uzbekturizm". On April 6, 2021, the Ministry of Tourism and Sports was established on the basis of the Ministry of Physical Education and Sports and the State Committee for the Development of Tourism by Decree No.

The focus of attention of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the development of the tourism of our country can be seen from the adoption of decrees and decisions adopted in recent years, including Resolution No. PQ-4095 of January 5, 2019 "On measures for the rapid

development of the tourism network", 19 of 2020 Resolution of June PQ-4755 "On additional measures to develop the tourism sector in strict compliance with the requirements of the enhanced sanitary-epidemiological safety regime", "On measures to further develop domestic and pilgrimage tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan" of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2021 Decree No. PF-6165 dated February 9, of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Tourism, Decree No. PF-6199 dated April 6, 2021 on measures to further improve the state management system in the fields of sports and cultural heritage, Decree No. PQ-104 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 27, 2022 on additional measures related to the development of the service sector Decree No. PF-6199 of February 18, 2022 "On organizational measures to improve state management in the fields of tourism, cultural heritage and sports" and others.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

To the main directions of state policy in tourism today effective management of tourism facilities on the basis of public-private partnership and introduction of modern information technologies in this field, formation and implementation of a holistic concept of tourism development, orientation of national tourism products and brands to enter international tourism markets, integrated development of domestic, inbound and outbound tourism, tourism services development of competition in the market is included. In particular, great attention is paid to planning and designing in areas with potential for placing tourism objects, that is, to expanding and activating regional tourist potential.

With the above-mentioned documents, along with the development of the institutional status of tourism, comprehensive measures are being implemented to attract tourists, that is, to increase the attractiveness of Uzbekistan's tourist products and create amenities for tourists, including the radical simplification of visa and customs clearance procedures, the free movement of transport and other services across our country. issues such as expansion of use, openness of tourist resources and readiness for consumption are being implemented step by step.

The third direction is to implement comprehensive measures to create favorable conditions for the development of business entities in the fields of tourism, accommodation and catering. This includes simplifying the registration and licensing of business entities, applying material support measures to them, reducing management in the tourism sector to the local level, simplifying the activities of accommodation entities, simplifying the procedure for providing tourist services, reducing the tax burden, and others.

As a result of the implemented measures, in the first place, an increase in the flow of tourists was observed in our country. (Table 1)

Table 1

Information on the number of tourists entering and leaving the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2014-2021*

Years	Those who entered, a thousand people	Annual change, %	Those who left, a thousand people	Annual change, %
2014	1938.0	100	4225.9	100
2015	2034.3	104.97	4868.6	115.21
2016	2157.7	106.06	5310.0	109.07
2017	2847.9	131.99	6823.9	128.51

2018	6433.0	225.88	13838.6	202.80
2019	8279.0	128.69	12932.6	93.45
2020	1504.1	18,17	2001.5	15.48
2021	1881.3	125.07	2194.8	109.65

*The table was compiled by the author based on the data of the statistical bulletin of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the main indicators of the development of tourism and recreation in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2018-2021

RESEARCH RESULTS

First of all, the formation of a stable trend of numerical growth of inbound and outbound tourism within the observed period. By 2019, the interest in Uzbekistan's tourism reached a peak, which coincided with the attention of the population of our country to tourism. Inbound tourism quadrupled in 2019 compared to 2014, while outbound tourism tripled.

The second trend is the numerical approach of inbound tourism to outbound tourism, that is, the influence of the tourism industry's contribution to the export of services.

Analyzing the flow of tourists from a scientific and methodological point of view, we should pay attention to the accuracy and objectivity of the data. In this regard, we refer to another source, that is, the publications of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, including statistical bulletins "The main indicators of the development of tourism and recreation in the Republic of Uzbekistan". Based on this source, the flow of tourists is as follows (Table 2).

Table 2

Information on the number of incoming and outgoing tourists in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2016-2021

Years	Inbound tourism, thousand people	Annual change, %	Outbound tourism, thousand people	Annual change, %
2016	2027.0	100	3847.8	100
2017	2690.1	132.71	5182.5	134.69
2018	5346.2	198.74	8594.8	165.84
2019	6748.5	126.23	8437.8	98.17
2020	1504.1	22,28	2001.5	23.72
2021	1881.3	125.06	2194.8	109.65

*The table was compiled by the author based on the data of the statistical bulletin of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the main indicators of the development of tourism and recreation in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2018-2021

We believe that the reason for the difference in data lies in the different sources of statistical observation. In the first case, the data is based on declarations filled out by citizens by the border-customs authorities, and in the second case, the data is explained by the statistics of enterprises and organizations engaged in providing services to visitors and collective accommodation (tourist companies, collective, specialized, individual and other means of accommodation). At the same time, it should be taken into account that one person may be counted several times in the total number of arrivals and departures in the statistics.

In the analysis of the tourist flow of Uzbekistan, the analysis of visits by goals is also important. Such an analysis helps to assess the level of attractiveness of tourist resources of our country. The composition of tourists entering Uzbekistan can be seen from the table below (Table 3).

Table 3

Composition of visitors to Uzbekistan in 2018-2021 by purpose*

Objectives	Number of visitors, thousand people				Share of the total number, %			
	2018	2019	2020	2021	2018	2019	2020	2021
Eliminating relatives	4708.9	5520.6	1321.4	1613.1	73.2	66.68	87.8	85.7
Reading	12.9	21.4	4.7	6.4	0.2	0.26	0.3	0.34
Job	38.6	54.0	0	0	0.6	0.65	0	0
Treatment	51.5	55.5	15.0	32.4	0.8	0.67	1.0	1.72
Tourism (leisure and recreation)	456.7	1043.9	129.6	155.0	7.1	12.61	8.6	8.24
Regarding the service	57.9	53.1	17.4	60.7	0.9	0.64	1.2	3.22
Permanent residence	77.2	53.6	0	0	1.2	0.65	0	0
Commerce	51.5	53.9	16.3	136.4	0.8	0.65	1.1	0.72
Transit	585.4	883.0	0	0	9.1	10.67	0	0
Other	392.4	540.0	0	0	6.1	6.52	0	0
Total	6433.0	8279.0	1504.1	1881.3	100	100	100	100
Of these, for business purposes (service commerce)	109.4	107.0	33.7	74348	1.7	1.29	2.3	3.95

*The table was compiled by the author based on the data of the statistical bulletin of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the main indicators of the development of tourism and recreation in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2018-2021

DISCUSSION

As it can be seen from this table, there are not many persons entering Uzbekistan with business goals. For example, if we include business tourism for service and commercial purposes. This category of tourists made up 1.7% in 2018, 1.29% in 2019, 2.3% in 2020, and 3.95% in 2021.

The composition of the number of tourists who left the territory of Uzbekistan is somewhat different by purpose (Table 4).

Table 4

Composition of those who left Uzbekistan in 2018-2021 by goals*

Objectives	The number of people who left, thousand people				Share of the total number, %			
	2018	2019	2020	2021	2018	2019	2020	2021
Eliminating	7971.0	7599.3	1694.5	1617.1	57.6	58.76	84.7	73.6

relatives								
Reading	55.3	104.4	107.6	189.0	0.4	0.81	5.4	8.6
Job	4137.6	3452.5	0	0	29.9	26.70	0	0
Treatment	55.6	37.2	16.5	23.9	0.4	0.29	0.8	1.08
Tourism (leisure and recreation)	401.3	606.1	158.5	349.2	2.9	4.68	7.9	15.9
Regarding the service	110.7	90.8	24.4	15.6	0.8	0.70	1.2	0.7
Permanent residence	456.7	369.2	0	0	3.3	2.85	0	0
Commerce	0	53.7	0	0	0	0.42	0	0
Transit	110.7	619.5	0	0	0.8	4.79	0	0
Other	539.7	0	0	0	3.9	0	0	0
Total	13838.6	12932.6	2001.5	2194.8	100	100	100	100
Of these, for business purposes (service commerce)	110.7	144.5	24.4	15.6	0.8	1.12	1.22	0.7

*The table was compiled by the author based on the data of the statistical bulletin of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the main indicators of the development of tourism and recreation in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2018-2021

It can be seen that in the flow of tourists leaving Uzbekistan, the share of those who indicated the purpose of business was 0.8% in 2018, and 1.12% in 2019. In 2020 - 1.22%, and in 2021 - 0.7%.

The information obtained from the tourism page of the open data portal of the Republic of Uzbekistan contains the following information (tables 5-6).

Table 5

Distribution of the number of foreign citizens who came to the Republic of Uzbekistan for the purpose of travel in 2021, people.*

t/r	Purposes of the trip	Number	Percentage, %
1	Total	1881345	100
2	Regarding the service	60704	3.2
3	Learning objectives	6416	0.34
5	Leisure and recreation	155068	8.25
6	Eliminating relatives	1613109	85.7
7	Treatment goals	32404	1.73
9	Commercial purposes	13644	0.73

*The table was compiled by the author based on the data of the statistical bulletin of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the main indicators of the development of tourism and recreation in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2021

6 - table

Distribution of the number of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan who left for travel purposes in 2021, people.*

t/r	Purposes of the trip	Number	Percentage, %
1	Total	2194847	100
2	Regarding the service	15586	0.72
3	Learning objectives	189052	8.62
5	Leisure and recreation	349190	15.9
6	Eliminating relatives	1617108	73.68
7	Treatment goals	23911	1.08

*The table was compiled by the author based on the data of the statistical bulletin of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the main indicators of the development of tourism and recreation in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2021

As can be seen from the above tables, there are several specific methods of registration of tourist flows and data collection, and some data may have a low level of objectivity.

When analyzing the state of the tourism sector, the study of domestic tourism occupies an important place, since the majority of tourist flows are related to the travel of citizens around the country (Table 7).

7 – table

In 2018-2021, the structure of trips of citizens of Uzbekistan to the country by purpose

Objectives	Number of trips made within the country, thousand trips				Share of the total number, %			
	2018	2019	2020	2021	2018	2019	2020	2021
vacation, leisure and recreation	31294.2	14438.2	10372.0	15865.3	26.3	13.3	9.3	13.6
to visit relatives and acquaintances	20573.1	57337.2	55775.2	58613.7	17.3	52.8	49.9	50.4
education and training	4377.8	873.0	866.4	597.9	3.7	0.8	0.8	0.5
treatment and recovery	14986.9	3911.2	3625.8	2279.9	12.6	3.6	3.2	1.9

visiting religious places and shrines	21055.2	9019.7	3440.0	3688.8	17.7	8.3	3.1	3.2
making purchases	9957.8	18843.9	34272.6	30703.6	8.3	17.4	30.6	26.4
other personal goals	9546.4	2110.7	2058.3	3081.6	8	1.9	1.8	2.6
employment and professional goals	7302.7	1983.5	1317.7	1508.2	6.1	1.8	1.2	1.3
Total	119094,1	108517.4	111728.0	116339.1	100	100	100	100

*The table was compiled by the author based on the data of the statistical bulletin of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the main indicators of the development of tourism and recreation in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2018-2021

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, if we analyze this table, some types of travel purposes of citizens of Uzbekistan have not reached a sufficient level. For example, if we include work-related professional and educational and professional training purposes in business tourism, the category of tourists for work-related and professional purposes will be 6.1% in 2018, 1.8% in 2019, 1.2% in 2020, and 2021 1.3%, another category of tourists for educational and professional training purposes was 3.7% in 2018, 0.8% in 2019, 0.8% in 2020, 0.5% in 2021. It can be seen that due to the Covid-19 pandemic, in 2020, the types of tourist's work-related and professional, as well as educational and professional training goals did not fail to have an impact. The lowest indicator was observed in 2020.

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